

SITE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1058 ☐ Natural ☐ Anthropic	Gabilan
In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No		In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No		Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #:	2750-57	Photo Model: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 423
DEFINITION wall running N-S between areas B+F			Covered by ☒ SU: 0	Fills ☒ SU: 1175	Filled by ☐ SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☐ Color ☒ Composition ☐ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☒ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☐ Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive Compaction ☐ Hard ☐ Compact ☐ Friable ☐ Loose ☐ Soft Color ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)
☐ Pottery ☐ Tiles ☐ Amphorae ☐ Dolia ☐ Mosaic tiles ☐ Mortar ☐ Coins ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Glass	☐ Nails ☐ Marble ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Other (specify)	☐ Tuff (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)			
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						Depth: ☐ Original ☒ Not Original
Northern Limit		☐ Original ☐ Not Original ☒ Excavation Limit				
Southern Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit				
Western Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry): 363, 387		
Is abutted by: 5018				Abuts:		
Is covered by: 1174				Covers:		
Is cut by:				Cuts:		
Is filled by:				Fills: 1175		
OBSERVATIONS This wall has been recorded since GPR '10, but it's full extent to the south was only discovered in GPR '12.						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: The wall marks the north-eastern edge of trench F in GPR '12 Shape: linear						
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions): Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Nature of the interface with layer below: ☐ sharp ☐ diffuse ☐ convoluted ☐ other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): 			

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: *N-S running, faced to W*

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify) *polygonal info blocks*

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify) *Opus quasi polygonatum*

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

length: _____ width: 0,57m height: 1,37m max.

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

The wall served as retaining wall for a street, it shows in terms of its building technique great similarities to wall 5008, but only in the deeper part of the masonry. It stays to be researched, whether SU 1058 contains different phases.

In 2010 it was believed that SU 1058 runs all the way down into the area urbana. Now we know that it is not.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by: *CHM*

Revised by: *CHM*

PDF'd by:

Entered by:

on: *1.8.2012*

on: *1.8.2012*

on:

on:

One big long wall, but at least 4 different walls. We kept the SU 1058 for the northern part of what we originally believed to be one long wall only. Therefore we didn't have to change the recording from trench A (2009-2010).